

Suchresultate zur Studie Digital mobility outcomes in 4 populations

Suchprotokolle:

 Cinahl 14112019.pdf

 Cochrane 14112019.txt

 IEEE Xplore 14112019.pdf

 Scopus 14112019.pdf

 Cochrane 14112019.pdf

 Embase 14112019.pdf

 Medline 14112019.pdf

 Web of Science 14112019.pdf

	Deduplication	
	Before	after
Medline	6'358	6'128
Embase	12'307	6'661
Cinahl	2'744	605
Cochrane	3'593	1'230
Scopus	8'755	1'929
Web of Science	9'031	2'414
IEEE Xplore	861	547
Pool	43'649	19'514

Reference files: gait parameters 14112019.enlx

Reference list before deduplication:

- All References (43649)
- Configure Sync...
- Recently Added (43649)
- Unfiled (39195)
- Trash (0)
- My Groups**
 - Cinahl (2744)
 - Cochrane (3593)
 - Embase (12307)
 - IEEE Xplore (861)
 - Medline (6358)
 - Scopus (8755)
 - Web of Science (9031)

Reference list after deduplication:

- All References (19514)
- Configure Sync...
- Recently Added (0)
- Unfiled (17737)
- Trash (0)
- My Groups**
 - Cinahl (605)
 - Cochrane (1230)
 - Embase (6661)
 - IEEE Xplore (547)
 - Medline (6128)
 - Scopus (1929)
 - Web of Science (2414)